

Choice paralysis and decision-making skills among nursing students

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Abstract

Nursing students face many choices every day, from being a junior nursing student to being a senior nursing student. The study can lead to an opportunity to recognize the significance of choice paralysis in any area where individuals are needed to choose from an assortment of options. The study aimed to determine the choice paralysis and decision-making skills among nursing students. The sample for this study consisted of one hundred four (104) nursing students. The instrument utilized for this study was a 6-point Likert scale questionnaire. The purposive sampling technique was used in this study. The results for the choice paralysis indicate that nursing students when under the influence of choice paralysis felt overwhelmed by the numerous choices presented to them, hesitated after seeing the choices and finds it challenging to choose. While for decision-making, this indicates that they like to consult with others and knows that their decision making is a logical process. A Pearson's r data analysis revealed a low positive correlation ($r= 0.353$, $p= 0.01$). This implies that choice paralysis has a low significant in nursing students decision-making skills.

Keywords: *Choice paralysis; Decision-making; Nursing students; Choice overload; Decisions.*

To cite this article:

Lomod, A. M., Bartolome, A. R. B., Bayocboc, J. J. J., Buenviaje, E. J. B., Cusilit, A. K. U., Gabanto, D. A. R., Obiekezie, J. A., Sison, C. E., & Tu, C. S. (2022). Choice paralysis and decision-making skills among nursing students. *Faculty Research Journal – Nursing*, 8, 17-25.

Introduction

Choice paralysis comes to a step before analysis paralysis, where the act of making a choice seems overwhelming before an individual even analyzes the situation. Choice paralysis happens when deciding becomes too daunting due to the various possible consequences and risks associated with making the wrong decision. Having so many good choices can be mentally draining because each one must be compared against the others to determine which would be better. According to Kurien et al. (2014), analysis paralysis or paralysis by analysis is the situation of over-analyzing or overthinking a situation to the point that no choice or act is taken, results in the result being paralyzed. A choice can be too complex, with too many specific choices, to the point that no decision is made, rather than trying something and changing if a significant issue occurs.

According to Gati et al. (2020), decision-making is choosing a straightforward course of action despite many choices that may have done to achieve a specific goal. Decision-making skills reflect the competence of a person to choose between two or more alternatives. Once it processes all available information and talks to the right points of contact involved in a particular situation, one may decide. Decision-making skills can mean the difference between making a good decision and making a bad one. Given that a person makes thousands of decisions every day, all of which have effects that can yield positive or negative outcomes, it provides a regular opportunity to enhance an individual's ability to make decisions.

As broad as the nurse's role in the city, they are pounded with clinical choices that require decision-making skills that may develop over time. Even before they become a registered nurse, they face hard decisions even as a student nurse. They are making clinical decisions essential in nursing, as it holds each client's safety. Medical professionals make clinical decisions regularly, but the mechanisms that surround them are incompletely known.

Nursing students face many challenges that lead them to a situation where they need to choose. Factors that influence nursing students' decision-making will shed light, and this can help obtain and identify the effects of choice paralysis on students. Nursing students face many choices every day, from being a junior nursing student to being a senior nursing student. Not to mention the number of choices or options after graduating, choosing what to do next and what specializations they want to pursue. If they want to teach, which subjects they would want to teach and specialize in. The study can lead to an opportunity to recognize the significance of choice paralysis in any area where individuals are needed to choose from an assortment of options. This research can also understand the students' concerns and difficulties when confronted with an abundance of choices and choice paralysis.

The study can accommodate insightful awareness regarding choice paralysis and decision-making skills on nursing students. The results may also benefit the students since they will provide insights into choice paralysis. Through this, students and teachers will be aware of the choice paralysis phenomena and help them when faced with an abundance of choices. Teachers will know the sensations of choice paralysis and apply the obtained knowledge to reduce the choice paralysis effects on students. The course can also benefit the parents. The study's results can help them guide their children when faced with a multitude of options. It can also benefit society, wherein the study's results can help them understand the choice paralysis phenomena and its effects that will help the industry and academic community.

The study aimed to determine the choice paralysis and decision-making skills among nursing students. It aimed to determine the demographic profile of nursing students and find out if there is a significant relationship between choice paralysis and decision-making skills among nursing students.

Review of Related Literature

Choice Overload

According to Chernev et al. (2015), there are four critical factors in choice overload: choice set complexity, preference uncertainty, decision task difficulty, and decision goal. These four key aspects affect the impact of the choice overload. Chernev et al. illustrated that each element significantly impacts choice overload by having an effort-minimizing plan, more excellent choice set complexity, higher preference uncertainty, and choice overload can result from a high degree of decision task complexity.

According to Kurien et al. (2014), an optimal or "magic" number of choices would make the decision-making process more comfortable and avoid the negative impacts of said decision. The study showed that too few options and too many choices have the same effects; few choices and too many choices lead an individual to be unsatisfied and postpone their determination. They stated the paradox of choice where he discovered the optimal selection of different options is tough and proposed several tips to lessen and avoid the effects of analysis paralysis. The word "analysis paralysis" or "analysis paralysis" refers to over-analyzing (or over-thinking) a situation or quoting a source so that a decision or action is never actually made, thus paralyzing the result. It is a common myth that as more options are provided to the customer by the seller, sales will grow. When buyers are overwhelmed with options, they are reported to put off making a purchase decision, while when there are fewer options, they are reported to close deals more quickly. Consumers buy less when they have more options; when making decisions, people often simplify by using the wrong criteria; and having more options leads to more serious disappointment because expectations are increased.

According to Schwartz (2015), he pointed out in his book *The Paradox of Choice*, “We live our lives under the impression that choice is good and therefore assume that more choice will do us good and will benefit us.” Schwartz tackled the paradoxical idea of choices. If there are too many options, it makes individuals less happy, less satisfied, and can even lead to paralysis with their selection. Schwartz also stated that having more is less. Our autonomy and, as a result, our well-being is dependent on our ability to make choices. However, in recent years, psychologists have delved further into it and have gradually shown that just as having too little choice can be detrimental, having too much choice can be harmful as well. Schwartz’s book supports the concept of having too many options to choose from is counterproductive. To examine that choice overload does affect decision paralysis, they researched in a laboratory and asked college students to evaluate various gourmet chocolates. The participants were asked which chocolate they prefer based on description and appearance. Some students were asked to choose from 6 different chocolates, and the rest is to choose from 30. While in the next room, the students were offered the opportunity to opt between a bar of cash and chocolate as a token of appreciation for participating in the study. The conclusion was that the students given six choices were more satisfied with their decision than those who chose from 30 and chose chocolate rather than cash. It demonstrates that as the number of options rises, so does the amount of cognitive work needed to compare them, as well as the risk of making a poor decision that leads to regret.

Decision-making

Dietrich (2010) asserts that different factors can affect how decisions are made. Their decision-making is influenced by some factors, including age, cognitive biases, personal relevant beliefs, experience, and an increase in commitment. This demonstrates how multiple factors affect the process of making decisions.

Fasolo et al. (2009) claim that although consumers are drawn to huge assortments, the abundance of options confuses and discourages them. Choice exacerbates the effect of choice paralysis and requires more work to make decisions in large, dense, high-entropy assortments than in tiny, low-density, low-entropy assortments.

People are presented with a wide range of decisions on a daily basis, both big and small. Theories and heuristics have been established to understand how people make decisions both now and in the future, as well as what influences decision-making. Experience (Conklin & Boulamatsi, 2020), cognitive biases (Stanovich & West, 2008), age and individual differences (Weller et al., 2018), belief in personal importance (Acevedo & Krueger, 2004), and an elevation of engagement (Leung et al., 2021) are all factors that affect people’s decisions.

Heuristics offer a framework for developing the correct choices quickly and easily (Shah & Oppenheimer, 2008). Heuristics reduce the amount of effort people must put in by giving them a general path to follow (West et al., 2008). The application of heuristics including influences that impact decision-making is necessary for critical thinking. There is evidence that this can be taught, which helps people learn when and how to make the best decisions in a range of situations (Nokes et al., 2007).

People make choices on a variety of topics. They make political decisions, personal choices, such as some medical decisions, romantic decisions, work decisions, and financial decisions, as well as several other decisions. The method of decision-making is often important to the decision at hand. Some choices appear to be straightforward and easy, while others appear to be more complex and require a multi-step decision-making process. Ahmady and Shahbazi (2020), Marques (2019), and Tang et al. (2017) stated that different factors are affecting choice paralysis and decision making and that each element can be modified to lessen or to avoid the effects of choice paralysis and to understand the factors that influence decision making process. Research focused on the business aspect of decision-making and foreign research settings. Thus, our study intends to focus on the academic part of decision making and having a Filipino university as our research setting.

Conceptual Paradigm

Choice paralysis is a decision that overwhelms nursing students due to many Potential outcomes that may result from making the wrong choice. It affects the decision-making skills of nursing students by having too many choices that hindrance nursing students from deciding on what they want.

Figure 1. Conceptual Paradigm

Methodology

This research used a descriptive correlational design. A descriptive correlational design by Polit and Beck (2012) helps to describe the study variables and their corresponding relationships that occur naturally between and among them. The researchers selected this research design to measure the choice paralysis phenomenon, to additionally look and explore the relationship between choice paralysis and student's decision making.

Research was conducted among selected nursing students from selected nursing schools in the Philippines, such as St. Dominic College of Asia, the University of Makati, Tytana College, Velez College in Cebu, and San Pedro College in Davao. The primary reason why the researchers decided to utilize the said locale is significant because of its availability and accessibility to the respondents.

The respondents were selected based on the following inclusion criteria:

- a.) Student must be currently enrolled under the Bachelor of Science in nursing program.
- b.) There is no age limit as long as the student is enrolled in the said program.

Purposive sampling is used wherein researchers rely on their judgment in terms of selecting population to participate in the study. Though it may be cost-effective and timely, it has a low level of reliability and a high level of bias.

The questionnaire was divided into three consecutive parts. Part I is the Conforme, Part II is the section that attempted to document views of Choice Paralysis, and Part III is the section that attempted to document the participant's response to Decision Making. Each Respondent was asked to rate their responses using a 6-point Likert scale for part II (1=strongly agree, 2=agree, 3=slightly agree, 4=slightly disagree, 5=disagree, and 6=strongly disagree) and for part III (1=very infrequently or never, 2=infrequently, 3=quite infrequently, 4=quite frequently, 5=frequently, 6=very frequently or always.) Potential participants had the option of previewing the survey before choosing to participate.

This research presented its relevance to a current issue on the study’s significance by describing its importance supported by describing the current problem status. To achieve social value, the researchers disseminated research results to the intended audience, including the participants. The researchers also valued the participants’ right to fair treatment on participant selection and honored all agreements, beliefs, habits, and lifestyles. The researchers also ensured that the participants are competent to participate in the study and understand relevant information without being subjected to coercion, undue influence, or inducement concerning the right to self-determination and full disclosure. This research study did not pose any risk and harm to the participants and institutions to warrant the right to freedom from liability and discomfort. The participants’ involvement in this research study did not expose the participants to any damage.

The researchers used frequency to sum up the results of all gathered data. The data which utilized frequency was gathered from the results of the questionnaire. The researchers used percentage to represent statistics. Choice paralysis and decision-making were determined by means, which are the sum of the scores. The mean value is calculated by dividing the total number of values into the data set by the sum of all values in the data set. The mean formula was used to compute the mean value of each response in the questionnaires. Pearson R was used to measure the strength between the two variables.

Results and Discussion

Table 1. Respondent’s Demographic Profile (n=104)

Profile	Variable	Frequency	Percent
Age	18-20 years old	73	70.2
	21-30 years old	31	29.8
Gender	Female	85	81.7
	Male	19	18.3
Civil Status	Single	103	99.0
	Married	1	1.0
Academic Status	Full time student	104	100.0
School Enrolled	St. Dominic College of Asia	69	66.3
	University of Makati	22	21.2
	Manila Tytana Colleges	2	1.9
	Velez College in Cebu	8	7.7
	San Pedro College in Davao	3	2.9
Year Level	1st year	26	25.0
	2nd year	59	56.7
	3rd year	12	11.5
	4th year	7	6.7
School Category	Private	81	77.9
	Public	23	22.1
Region	Region 1 (Ilocos Region)	1	1.0
	Region 3 (Central Luzon)	1	1.0
	Region 4A (CALABARZON)	64	61.5
	Region 7 (Central Visayas)	6	5.8
	Region 8 (Eastern Visayas)	1	1.0
	Region 11 (Davao Region)	4	3.8
	NCR (National Capital Region)	27	26.0

Table 1 indicates the frequency and percentage of respondents from nursing students in terms of their demographic profile. The data shows that the ages 18 to 20 has a frequency of 73 or while the ages 21 to 30 has a frequency of 31 or 29.8%. Therefore, most of the respondents are in the ages of 18 to 20 (70.2%) while the least number of respondents come from the ages of 21 to 30 (29.8%).

In terms of civil status, almost all of the respondents are identified as single (99.0%), while only one is married (1.0%). It is revealed that all of the respondents are taking their education as full-time students. In terms of their enrolled school, the data shows that respondents from St. Dominic College of Asia have a frequency of 69 or 66.3% while those who enrolled at University of Makati have a frequency of 22 or 21.2%. There are 8 frequencies or 7.7% for those enrolled at Velez College in Cebu and 3 frequencies or 2.9% for those currently enrolled at San Pedro College in Davao. Lastly, those respondents currently enrolled at Manila Tytana College have a frequency of 2 or 1.9%. Therefore, most of the respondents are currently enrolled at St. Dominic College of Asia while least number of respondents are enrolled at Manila Tytana Colleges.

In terms of their year level, the data shows that those who are in their second year level have a frequency of 59 or 56.3% while those who are in their first year level have a frequency of 26 or 25%. There are 12 frequencies or 7.7% for those who are in their 3rd year level and 7 frequencies or 6.7% for those who are in their 4th year level. Therefore, most of the respondents are in their 2nd year level while the least number of respondents are in their 4th year level.

In terms of their school category, those respondents who studied in private school have frequency of 81 or 77.9% while those who studied in public school have a frequency of 23 or 22.1%. Therefore, most of the respondents are taking their education in private school.

In terms of the region where they currently reside, those who live in Region 4A (CALABARZON) have a frequency of 64 or 61.5% while in the National Capital Region have a frequency of 27 or 26%. There are 6 frequencies or 5.8% for those who reside in Region 7 (Central Visayas) and 4 frequencies or 3.8% in Region 11 (Davao Region). Lastly, those who reside in Region 1 (Ilocos Region), Region 3 (Central Luzon), and Region 8 (Eastern Visayas) all have a frequency of 1 or 1.0%. Therefore, most of the respondents reside in Region 4A or also known as CALABARZON.

Tables 2 and 3 present the data that assesses whether there is a significant relationship between choice paralysis and decision-making skills among nursing students. In order to determine the decision and conclusion for the assessment, the P-value less than 0.05 (<0.05) means that it is statistically significant and indicates strong evidence to reject the null hypothesis. However, if the P-value is higher than 0.05, it means it has no significant relationship which means that there is strong evidence to fail to reject null hypothesis.

Table 2. Significant Relationship

		Choice	Decision
Choice	Pearson Correlation	1	.353**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	104	104
Decision	Pearson Correlation	.353**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	104	104

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 3. Spearman Rho correlation

	Spearman Rho	P-value	Decision	Conclusion
Choice Paralysis vs. Decision-making Skills	0.343	0.000	Reject Null Hypothesis	Significant Weak Relationship

Using Kolmogrov-Smirnov Test, the Choice Paralysis has a test statistic of .106 with significance value of 0.006 followed by the Decision-Making Skills which has a test statistic of .083 with significance value of .071. All of the variable has a similar degree of freedom of 104. Using the Shapiro-Wilk Test, the

Choice Paralysis has a test statistic of .975 with significance value of .048 followed by the Decision-Making Skills which has a test statistic of .963 with significance value of .005. All of the variables have a similar degree of freedom of 104.

With the result using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test, it shows that the “Decision-making Skills” has a p-value higher than 0.05 but the “Choice Paralysis” is having a p-value less than 0.05 which means it is still deviate from a normal distribution. The p-value of both variables using Shapiro-Wilk Test is less than 0.05, thus, the data significantly deviate from a normal distribution. Therefore, the researchers should use non-parametric tests, specifically Spearman’s Rank-Order Correlation.

Table 4. Normality Tests

Factors	Kolmogorov-Smirnov			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
Choice Paralysis	.106	104	.006	.975	104	.048
Decision-Making Skills	.083	104	.071	.963	104	.005

Discussion

Respondents of all ages (18 through 40 and above) were represented, with slightly larger numbers in the lowest age bracket and the number of male respondents were fewer compared to females. The findings of this study showed that most of the respondents gathered are single and majority of the students are enrolled at St. Dominic College of Asia. Most of the samples were answered by second year students, and all of them are full-time students. Majority of the students gathered are in a private sectarian school.

Based on the results, this implies that nursing students when under the influence of Choice Paralysis felt overwhelmed by the numerous choices presented to them, hesitated after seeing the choices and finds it challenging to choose. But despite the difficulty, the result revealed that most of the students looked at every choice before deciding, based their choices on advantages, disadvantages, preferences, convenience, and also the results showed that students did not choose random options and they are also satisfied with their choices and chose what really mattered.

This result signifies that despite being faced with an abundance of choices, nursing students still consider every choice that they make. Previous research has not looked at how nursing students perceive or emanate the phenomena of choice paralysis, previous researches only looked at consumers and students in general. This study suggests that the results are consistent and this is a new result specifically for the nursing student population. Majority of the nursing students, when deciding, frequently take the safe option, but also works out the pros and cons. It also shows that they like to consult with others and knows that their decision making is a logical process. This implies that even in doubt, nursing students are thorough when deciding.

Conclusions

The researchers concluded that choice paralysis and decision-making skills are present in the nursing students when deciding on something. It affects the nursing students when they need to choose with having too many choices. Choice paralysis can be seen when they felt overwhelmed by the numerous choices presented to them, and they have been hesitant after seeing the options and finds it challenging to choose. Despite the difficulty, the result revealed that most of the students looked at every choice before deciding, based their choices on its advantages, disadvantages, preferences, convenience, and did not choose random options. They are satisfied with their choices and choose what matters.

This result signifies that despite being faced with an abundance of choices; nursing students still consider every choice that they make while the decision-making skills of nursing students see when they need to decide. They frequently take the safe options but also work out the pros and cons. They also like to consult with others and know that their decision-making is a logical process. It implies that even in doubt, nursing students are thorough when deciding.

Students should be able to recognize choice paralysis when experiencing it so that the students can take precautions and avoid the negative effects of this issue. In this way, the students can channel their energy in making a good decision without being hindered by the effects of choice paralysis. It is also recommended to parents to give their children a short lesson about choice paralysis and decision making and how to avoid it. In this way, they can guide their children towards making a good decision without being hindered by the effects of choice paralysis. It is recommended that the school administrators conduct short seminars that will teach the students about choice paralysis and how to avoid it.

Future researchers should study this in another context like in businesses and other organizations. They may use a psychological method to determine why choice paralysis occurs and the decision making of students. It is also recommended to use qualitative study for the purpose of being able to get more comparison and results that will be more comprehensive.

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